

ABOUT SOME OIKONYMS IN THE CHIMBAY DISTRICT

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Annotation. *This article examines oikonymic indicators in one of the historical cities of Karakalpakstan - Chimbay district. Oikonyms containing these indicators are analyzed using an example.*

Key words: *city, street, village, homeland, house.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются ойконимические индикаторы одного из исторических городов Каракалпакстана - Чимбайского района. Ойконимы, содержащие эти индикаторы, были проанализированы на примере.*

Ключевые слова: *город, улица, село, страна, дом.*

The toponyms of the Chimbay district have a significant place in the toponymy of Karakalpakstan. When studying district toponyms, we see names of places formed in the presence of oikonymic indicators. The toponyms of this region contain oikonymic indicators such as *qala* (city), *kóshe* (street), *awıl* (village), *baǵ* (garden), *jurt* (homeland), *tam* (old house), *úy* (house), *áwliye* (cemetery), and *meshit* (mosque). We would like to discuss some of the toponyms derived from this indicator in the Chimbay district.

Qala (city) is widespread in Iranian and Turkic toponymy. Regarding this indicator, A.Z.Rozenfeld states that it is frequently found in geographical names, spreading from the Middle East to the Iberian Peninsula [Rosenfeld A.Z. 1951]. In Iranian languages, a house on a hill surrounded by a fence was called so. Sometimes a simple hill was also called *qala* (city). In Arabic and Turkish, it appears as a house on a hill, a fortress, and in Kyrgyz as *qala* (city). In Uzbek language, this word was previously associated with a city or market, and those who brought goods from Russian cities and sold them were called *qalashılar* (city dwellers). In Karakalpak language, the word *qala* (city) means cultural, political, vocational trade center, large settlement, city, town [ҚҚТС, 1988:108]. Within the district, there are toponyms like Shımbay qalası and Yusupbiydiń qalası, formed with the word *qala* (city). The local population also uses the indicator *qala* (city) as a toponym.

Kóshe (street) is a place with rows of buildings on both sides, with transport

and pedestrian walkways in the middle [KKTTC, 1988:35]. This indicator participates in the formation of place names. E.M. Murzayev indicates that in ancient Chinese monuments *kóshe* (street) was known as *Guyci* [Murzaev E.M. 1974:292]. In most Turkic languages and Iranian languages, the word *kóshe* (street) means "settlement, street". Currently, it exists in many languages. This word, by its historical origin, is likely related to the Sogdian word *koca*. There are about 90 street names formed with this word in the district. Most of them are derived from personal names (historical figures, public figures, heroes, scholars, poets), while others are derived from historical events and folk epics: *Ajiniyaz kóshesi* (*Ajiniyaz Street*), *Ernazar Alakóz kóshesi* (*Ernazar Alakóz Street*), *Edige kóshesi* (*Edige Street*), *Tınıshlıq kóshesi* (*Tınıshlıq Street*).

The indicator *awıl* (village) refers to a settled area and is widespread in Karakalpak language. The indicator *awıl* (village) is widespread among Turkic and Mongolian-speaking peoples: *awıl* in Kazakh and Bashkir, *avıl* in Nogai and Tatar, *avul* in Kumyk, and *ayıl* in Altai. Synonyms for the word *awıl* are *qishloq* in Uzbek, *qishlaq* in Uyghur, *kıstak* in Kyrgyz, *suur* in Tuvan, *yel* in Chuvash, *kánd* in Azerbaijani, and *oba* in Turkmen. In Mongolian, the word *ail* means "meadow". In Old Turkic, the word *ağıl* means "cattle pen" [Abduvaliyev I., 1990:268].

In the toponymy of Chimbay, there are many geographical terms formed with the indicator *awıl* (village). Several villages are located in the district. Most of these villages are formed from ethnonyms and anthroponyms. For example: *Bessarı awıl* (*Bessari village*), *Sheriwshi awıl* (*Sheriwshi village*), *Kepe awıl* (*Kepe village*), *Beksiyiq awıl* (*Beksiyiq village*), *Qostamǵalı awılı* (*Qostamgali village*), *Qutıbay awıl* (*Qutıbay village*), *Darıbay awıl* (*Darıbay village*), *Qalmurat tope* (*Qalmurat tope*).

Baǵ (garden) is an indicator that participates in the formation of agronomic terms, but is not very productive: *Asqarbaydıń baǵı* (*Asqarbay's garden*), *Joldasbaydıń baǵı* (*Joldasbay's garden*).

Jurt (homeland) - currently this indicator is widely used as an oikonymic indicator in the sense of "village, populated area". Among Turkic peoples, the word *jurt* along with the meaning of "place of residence" or "dwelling place," also conveyed the meaning of "state, nation". In modern Turkic languages, this indicator is used in various phonetic variants. For example, in Kumyk, Nogai, Tatar, Turkmen, and Uzbek languages it appears as *yurt*, *yurd* in Azerbaijani, *yort* in Bashkir, *jurt* in Kyrgyz and Kazakh, *churt* in Tuvan and Khakas, *surt* in Yakut, and *yurt* in old Turkic. In Karakalpakstan, the element *jurt* is found within a number of toponyms. However, they are not frequently used within the toponyms of the studied regions: *Madiyarjurt*,

Saparbayjurt.

The indicator *tam* (old house) means "a house built of brick or mud walls" [KKTTC, 1992:269]. This indicator forms the toponyms of populated areas and is widespread in Eurasian toponymy. The word *tam* meaning "wall" has been known in most modern Turkic languages since ancient times: *dam* in Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Turkish, and Gagauz, *tam* in Kyrgyz and Uyghur, and *tom* in Uzbek. It is also used in terms specific to Turkic languages. In Chimbay, there are toponyms formed with the indicator *tam*: *Baltabaytam*, *Bestam*.

The word "úy" (house) has been used in Turkic languages since ancient times. In ancient Turkic written sources, the word "úy" (house) means "human dwelling" [Molov, S.E., 1951:366]. In the Chimbay region, the term with the component "úy" is used in the toponym *on eki úy* (twelve houses).

Áwliye (cemetery) - a place where the dead are buried, a powerful place, a place, a tomb, a grave [KKTTC, 1982:152]. It is considered a sacred place in Islam. In the district, there are more than 60 toponyms formed with the participation of this indicator. Most of them were created with the participation of anthroponyms and ethnonyms. In the spoken language of the people, the words "qoyımshılıq" and "qábiristan", synonymous with the indicator *áwliye* (cemetery), are also used. For example: *Ayımbet iyshan áwliyesi* (Ayımbet iyshan cemetery), *Orıs áwliye* (Orıs cemetery), and *Tóreniyaz axun qábiristanı* (cemetery of Tóreniyaz axun). The word "baba" (grandfather), sometimes found in toponyms, is used directly in the spoken language to mean a cemetery: to honor the memory of a grandfather. In the local language, this term refers to the Axunbaba cemetery.

Meshit (mosque) is an Arabic word for a place where Muslims pray in congregation. Some mosques served as centers of learning for children. There, during Friday and hayt prayers, imam-khatibs perform the xupta and exchange views on religious matters. This indicator is found in the toponyms of all districts of the republic.

The emergence of the term *meshit* is often linked to the subject that created it: *Ayımbet iyshan meshiti* (Ayımbet iyshan mosque), *Xan meshit* (Khan mosque). This indicator sometimes appears as a separate toponym in the spoken language of the people: *Meshit*.

In conclusion, many oikonymic indicators have been preserved within the toponyms of the district. The study of local toponyms and the oikonymic indicators involved in their formation plays an important role in the study of district toponyms.

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